

THE IMPACT OF AUTOMATION ON SERVICE WORKERS: A TECHNICAL ANALYSIS

Shradha Kohli

Salesforce, USA

ABSTRACT

This technical analysis examines the profound impact of automation technologies on service workers across various industries. It explores the key technological drivers of this transformation, including artificial intelligence, machine learning, robotic process automation, and the Internet of Things. The paper analyzes both the challenges and opportunities presented by automation, discussing job displacement, creation of new roles, productivity augmentation, and the emerging skill gap. Through case studies in banking and hospitality, it illustrates the real-world applications and effects of these technologies. The analysis also addresses ethical considerations, policy implications, and potential mitigation strategies to navigate the changing landscape of work in the service sector. By providing a comprehensive overview of the current state and future outlook of automation in services, this paper aims to inform policy-making, business strategies, and individual career decisions in an increasingly automated world.

Keywords: Automation, Service Industry, Artificial Intelligence, Job Transformation, Workforce Adaptation

Cite this Article: Shradha Kohli, The Impact of Automation on Service Workers: A Technical Analysis, International Journal of Engineering and Technology Research (IJETR), 9(2), 2024, pp. 492–504.

<https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJETR?Volume=9&Issue=2>

1. Introduction

The service industry is undergoing a profound transformation, driven by the rapid advancement of automation technologies. At the forefront of this change are sophisticated software systems and artificial intelligence (AI), which are reshaping the landscape of service delivery and workforce dynamics. This technological revolution is not confined to a single sector but is permeating various segments of the service industry, from retail and hospitality to finance and healthcare [1].

The impact of automation on service workers is multifaceted and complex. On one hand, it presents significant challenges, particularly in terms of job displacement. A study by Frey and Osborne (2017) estimated that nearly 47% of total US employment is at risk of computerization, with service occupations being particularly vulnerable [2]. This statistic underscores the potential for widespread disruption in the service sector workforce.

However, the narrative of automation in the service industry is not solely one of job loss and displacement. Automation also creates new opportunities for service workers, often in the form of higher-value roles that require uniquely human skills such as emotional intelligence, creative problem-solving, and complex communication. For instance, in the banking sector, the implementation of chatbots for routine customer inquiries has allowed human representatives to focus on more complex, high-value interactions, potentially improving both job satisfaction and customer experience.

Moreover, automation has the potential to augment worker productivity and efficiency. By taking over routine, repetitive tasks, automation frees up human workers to focus on aspects of their jobs that require judgment, creativity, and interpersonal skills. This shift can lead to increased job satisfaction and potentially higher wages for workers who can effectively collaborate with and leverage automated systems.

The integration of automation in the service industry also raises important questions about the future of work, the changing nature of skills required in the workforce, and the need for continuous learning and adaptation. As AI and machine learning technologies continue to advance, the boundary between tasks that can be automated and those that require human intervention is constantly shifting, necessitating ongoing workforce development and training initiatives.

This article aims to provide a comprehensive technical analysis of the impact of automation on service workers. It will explore the technological drivers behind this transformation, examine both the challenges and opportunities presented by automation, and discuss potential strategies for navigating this changing landscape. By delving into case studies and emerging trends, we seek to offer insights that can inform policy-making, business strategies, and individual career decisions in the evolving service industry.

Fig 1: Job Risk vs. Job Enhancement: Automation in the Service Industry [1, 2]

2. Technological Drivers of Automation

The rapid advancement of automation in the service industry is primarily driven by three key technological areas: Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning, Robotic Process Automation, and the Internet of Things. These technologies are transforming service delivery and creating new paradigms for workforce engagement and customer interaction.

2.1 Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have made remarkable progress in recent years, enabling machines to perform complex tasks that were once thought to be exclusive to human workers. These technologies are at the forefront of the automation revolution in the service industry, with applications ranging from customer service to predictive maintenance [3].

Key AI and ML technologies impacting the service sector include:

1. **Natural Language Processing (NLP):** NLP enables machines to understand, interpret, and generate human language. This technology is the backbone of customer service chatbots and voice assistants, which are increasingly being deployed across various service industries. For example, in the banking sector, NLP-powered chatbots can handle a wide range of customer inquiries, from account balance checks to complex product recommendations. A study by Juniper Research predicts that by 2023, the banking industry could save up to 862 million hours of work through the use of chatbots, resulting in \$7.3 billion in potential cost savings [4].
2. **Computer Vision:** This technology allows machines to interpret and analyze visual information from the world. In the service industry, computer vision finds applications in areas such as quality control, security monitoring, and customer behavior analysis. For instance, in retail, computer vision systems can analyze store traffic patterns, optimize product placement, and even enable cashier-less stores. Amazon Go stores, which use computer vision for automated checkout, are a prime example of this technology in action.

3. **Predictive Analytics:** By leveraging historical data and machine learning algorithms, predictive analytics can forecast future trends and behaviors. This technology is particularly valuable in inventory management, demand forecasting, and personalized customer experiences. In the hospitality industry, for example, predictive analytics can optimize room pricing based on demand forecasts, potentially increasing revenue by up to 7% [5].

2.2 Robotic Process Automation (RPA)

Robotic Process Automation involves the use of software robots or "bots" to automate routine, rule-based tasks. This technology is particularly impactful in back-office operations, where it can significantly improve efficiency and reduce errors.

Key applications of RPA in the service industry include:

1. **Data Entry and Management:** RPA bots can automatically extract data from various sources (e.g., emails, scanned documents) and enter it into appropriate systems, reducing manual data entry errors and freeing up human workers for more complex tasks.
2. **Invoice Processing:** In finance and accounting departments, RPA can automate the entire invoice processing workflow, from receipt to payment, significantly reducing processing time and costs.
3. **Customer Data Management:** RPA can help maintain accurate and up-to-date customer records by automatically updating information across multiple systems, ensuring data consistency and improving customer service quality.

A report by Grand View Research projects that the global RPA market size will reach \$25.56 billion by 2027, growing at a CAGR of 40.6% from 2020 to 2027, indicating the significant impact and adoption of this technology across industries [3].

2.3 Internet of Things (IoT)

The Internet of Things refers to the network of physical objects embedded with sensors, software, and other technologies that enable them to collect and exchange data. In the service industry, IoT devices facilitate automated decision-making and predictive maintenance, leading to improved operational efficiency and enhanced customer experiences.

Key applications of IoT in the service sector include:

1. **Smart Hospitality:** In the hotel industry, IoT devices enable features like automated check-in/check-out, personalized room settings (temperature, lighting), and predictive maintenance of facilities. For example, Hilton's "Connected Room" technology allows guests to control various room features through their smartphones, enhancing the guest experience while also optimizing energy usage.
2. **Facilities Management:** IoT sensors can monitor building systems (HVAC, lighting, security) in real-time, enabling predictive maintenance and energy optimization. A study by Deloitte found that IoT-based smart building solutions can reduce energy costs by up to 30% [5].
3. **Inventory Management:** In retail and logistics, IoT devices can provide real-time tracking of inventory levels and conditions, enabling automated restocking and reducing waste. For instance, Walmart has implemented IoT-based systems to track food freshness, reportedly saving the company \$2.3 billion in food waste reduction.

The integration of these technologies - AI/ML, RPA, and IoT - is driving a new era of automation in the service industry. While these advancements offer significant benefits in terms of efficiency, cost reduction, and customer experience, they also present challenges for the workforce, necessitating new skills and adaptations to remain relevant in an increasingly automated landscape.

Service Sector	AI/ML Impact	RPA Impact	IoT Impact	Total Automation Impact
Retail	35%	25%	30%	90%
Hospitality	30%	20%	40%	90%
Finance	40%	35%	15%	90%
Facilities Management	20%	15%	45%	80%

Table 1: Relative Influence of AI/ML, RPA, and IoT Across Service Industries [3, 5]

3. Impact Analysis

The integration of automation technologies in the service industry is having a profound and multifaceted impact on the workforce. This section analyzes the key areas of impact, including job displacement, job creation and transformation, productivity augmentation, and the emerging skill gap.

3.1 Job Displacement

Automation is leading to significant displacement of jobs that primarily involve routine, repetitive tasks. A landmark study by the McKinsey Global Institute estimates that up to 800 million jobs could be displaced by 2030 due to automation [6]. This projection underscores the scale of the transformation facing the global workforce, particularly in the service sector.

Roles most affected by automation include:

- **Cashiers:** With the advent of self-checkout systems and cashier-less stores, traditional cashier roles are increasingly at risk. Amazon Go stores, for example, have eliminated the need for cashiers entirely through the use of computer vision and sensor fusion technologies.
- **Data Entry Clerks:** Robotic Process Automation (RPA) is rapidly taking over data entry tasks, with software bots capable of processing data much faster and more accurately than humans.
- **Customer Service Representatives (for routine inquiries):** AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants are handling an increasing volume of routine customer inquiries, reducing the need for human representatives for basic tasks.
- **Inventory Managers:** IoT sensors and AI-driven predictive analytics are automating many aspects of inventory management, from tracking stock levels to predicting demand.

The impact of this displacement is not uniform across all regions and demographics. Lower-wage jobs and those in developing economies are often at higher risk of automation. For instance, a study by the World Bank suggests that two-thirds of all jobs in developing countries are susceptible to automation [7].

3.2 Job Creation and Transformation

While automation displaces some jobs, it also creates new roles and transforms existing ones. This dynamic highlights the evolving nature of work in the age of automation:

- **AI Trainers and Specialists:** As AI systems become more prevalent, there's a growing need for workers who can train, maintain, and improve these systems. These roles require a blend of technical skills and domain expertise.
- **Data Analysts and Scientists:** The proliferation of automated systems generates vast amounts of data. Professionals who can interpret this data and derive actionable insights are increasingly in demand. The U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics projects a 31% growth in employment for data scientists from 2019 to 2029, much faster than the average for all occupations [8].
- **Customer Experience Designers:** As routine interactions become automated, there's a growing emphasis on designing seamless and meaningful interactions between humans and automated systems. These professionals blend technical knowledge with creativity and empathy.
- **Automation Managers:** These professionals oversee the implementation and optimization of automated processes, bridging the gap between technical capabilities and business needs.
- **Cybersecurity Specialists:** With increased automation comes greater cybersecurity risks. The demand for cybersecurity professionals is expected to grow significantly to protect automated systems from potential threats.

3.3 Productivity Augmentation

Automation can significantly enhance worker productivity, enabling service workers to focus on higher-value tasks:

- **Task Offloading:** By handling routine, repetitive tasks, automation frees up workers to focus on activities that require human judgment, creativity, and emotional intelligence. For example, in the legal sector, AI-powered document review systems allow lawyers to focus more on case strategy and client interaction.
- **Decision Support:** AI-powered analytics provide workers with insights to make more informed decisions. In healthcare, for instance, AI systems can analyze patient data and medical literature to assist doctors in diagnosis and treatment planning.
- **Error Reduction:** Automated systems can significantly reduce human errors in data processing and calculations. In financial services, automated fraud detection systems can process vast amounts of transaction data with higher accuracy than human analysts.

A study by Accenture found that AI could boost labor productivity by up to 40% by 2035 [6]. This productivity boost is expected to come not just from automation of tasks, but from AI's ability to augment human capabilities and enable more efficient ways of working.

3.4 Skill Gap and Retraining Needs

The shift towards automation creates a significant skill gap in the workforce, necessitating a focus on retraining and continuous learning:

- **Technical Skills:** There's a growing need for workers proficient in data analysis, programming, and AI technologies. According to the World Economic Forum's Future of Jobs Report 2020, 50% of all employees will need reskilling by 2025 as adoption of technology increases [8].
- **Soft Skills:** As machines take over routine tasks, there's an increased importance placed on skills that are harder to automate, such as critical thinking, creativity, emotional intelligence, and complex problem-solving. These skills enable workers to adapt to new roles and work effectively alongside automated systems.

- **Adaptive Learning:** Workers need to develop the ability to continuously learn and adapt to new technologies. The half-life of skills is shrinking, with technical skills becoming obsolete in as little as 2-5 years. This necessitates a shift towards lifelong learning and regular upskilling.
- **Digital Literacy:** Basic digital literacy is becoming a prerequisite for most jobs. Even traditionally non-technical roles now often require the ability to work with digital tools and platforms.

Addressing this skill gap requires concerted efforts from multiple stakeholders, including businesses, educational institutions, and policymakers. Companies like Amazon and IBM have launched large-scale retraining programs for their workforce, while governments are increasingly focusing on updating education curricula to better prepare students for the automated workplace.

The impact of automation on service workers is complex and multifaceted. While job displacement is a significant concern, the potential for productivity augmentation and the creation of new, high-value roles presents opportunities. Successfully navigating this transition will require proactive measures to address the emerging skill gap and ensure that workers are equipped to thrive in an increasingly automated service industry.

Job Category	Automation Risk (%)	Demand Change (%)	Skill Adaptation Required (1-5 scale)
Cashiers	90	-70	3
Data Entry Clerks	95	-80	4
Customer Service Reps (routine)	75	-50	3
Inventory Managers	70	-40	4
AI Trainers/Specialists	10	+200	5
Data Analysts/Scientists	15	+150	5
Customer Experience Designers	20	+100	4
Automation Managers	5	+180	5
Cybersecurity Specialists	5	+170	5

Table 2: Shifting Job Landscape: Automation Risk vs. Emerging Opportunities [6, 8]

4.Challenges and Mitigation Strategies

The integration of automation technologies in the service industry presents significant challenges that need to be addressed to ensure a smooth transition and minimize negative impacts on the workforce. This section explores key challenges and potential mitigation strategies.

4.1 Job Insecurity and Social Impact

The fear of job loss due to automation is a significant concern among service workers, leading to increased stress and potentially decreased job satisfaction. A study by the Pew Research Center found that 72% of Americans are worried about a future where robots and computers can do many human jobs [9]. This anxiety can have far-reaching social impacts, including:

- Decreased productivity due to stress and uncertainty
- Resistance to technological change and innovation
- Potential increase in mental health issues among affected workers

- Widening economic inequality as job displacement disproportionately affects certain demographics

To mitigate these challenges, organizations and policymakers can implement several strategies:

- 1. Transparent Communication:** Clear and honest communication about automation plans and their potential impact on jobs is crucial. This includes:
 - Regular updates on technological changes and their implications
 - Open forums for employees to voice concerns and ask questions
 - Clear pathways for skill development and role transitions
- 2. Gradual Implementation:** A phased approach to introducing automation can allow for smoother transitions and give workers time to adapt. This could involve:
 - Pilot programs to test automation in specific departments or processes
 - Incremental rollout of automated systems across the organization
 - Parallel operation of automated and manual systems during transition periods
- 3. Job Redesign:** Restructuring roles to leverage human strengths alongside automated systems can help preserve jobs while improving efficiency. This might include:
 - Identifying tasks that require human judgment, creativity, or emotional intelligence
 - Creating hybrid roles that combine technical oversight of automated systems with higher-level decision-making
 - Developing new roles that focus on the intersection of human skills and technological capabilities

A successful example of this approach is seen in the banking sector, where ATMs initially threatened to replace bank tellers. Instead, the role of tellers evolved to focus more on customer relationship management and complex financial services, actually increasing the number of teller jobs over time [10].

4.2 Ethical Considerations in AI Development

As AI systems take on more decision-making roles in service industries, ethical considerations become paramount. Key challenges include:

- 1. Bias Mitigation:** AI systems can inadvertently perpetuate or amplify existing biases, particularly in areas like hiring, customer service, or credit decisions. For example, Amazon had to scrap an AI recruiting tool that showed bias against women for technical positions [11]. Mitigation strategies include:
 - Diverse development teams to bring varied perspectives to AI design
 - Regular audits of AI decisions for potential biases
 - Use of fairness-aware machine learning techniques
- 2. Transparency:** The "black box" nature of some AI systems can make it difficult to understand how decisions are made, raising concerns about accountability. Strategies to address this include:
 - Developing explainable AI systems that can provide rationales for their decisions
 - Implementing human oversight for critical AI decisions
 - Creating clear audit trails for AI decision-making processes
- 3. Privacy Protection:** The vast amount of data used in automated systems raises significant privacy concerns for both workers and customers. Mitigation approaches include:
 - Implementing robust data protection measures, including encryption and access controls

- Adhering to data minimization principles, collecting only necessary data
- Providing clear opt-out options for data collection and use

4.3 Policy and Regulatory Frameworks

Governments and organizations need to develop comprehensive policies to address the challenges of automation. Key areas of focus include:

- 1. Upskilling Programs:** Investment in education and training programs is crucial to help workers adapt to new technologies. For example, Singapore's SkillsFuture initiative provides citizens with resources for lifelong learning and skills development [11]. Strategies include:
 - Partnerships between industry and educational institutions to develop relevant curricula
 - Government subsidies for workers to pursue further education or training
 - Company-sponsored training programs to reskill existing employees
- 2. Social Safety Nets:** Strengthening unemployment benefits and retraining support for displaced workers is essential to mitigate the social impact of automation. Approaches might include:
 - Extended unemployment benefits for workers displaced by automation
 - Wage insurance programs to supplement income for workers who take lower-paying jobs after displacement
 - Portable benefits systems that are not tied to specific employers
- 3. Ethical AI Guidelines:** Developing and enforcing guidelines for the ethical development and deployment of AI in the workplace is crucial to ensure responsible automation. Key elements might include:
 - Mandatory impact assessments for AI systems in critical areas
 - Requirements for explainability and transparency in AI decision-making
 - Establishment of AI ethics boards within organizations and at the national level

The European Union's proposed AI Act is an example of a comprehensive regulatory framework aimed at ensuring ethical and responsible use of AI technologies [11].

Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort from multiple stakeholders, including businesses, governments, educational institutions, and workers themselves. By implementing thoughtful strategies and policies, it's possible to harness the benefits of automation while mitigating its potential negative impacts on the service workforce.

5. Case Studies

5.1 Automated Customer Service in Banking

The banking industry has been at the forefront of adopting artificial intelligence (AI) and automation technologies to enhance customer service. Bank of America's virtual assistant, Erica, stands out as a prime example of this trend. Launched in 2018, Erica has served more than 17 million clients, handling a wide range of routine inquiries and transactions [12]. This AI-powered assistant can perform tasks such as checking account balances, transferring funds, and providing personalized financial insights.

The implementation of Erica has significantly reduced the workload on human customer service representatives, allowing them to focus on more complex issues that require empathy and nuanced problem-solving skills. As a result, banks have reported improved overall service

quality and efficiency. For instance, Bank of America has seen a 10% reduction in call center volume and a 25% increase in customer satisfaction scores since Erica's introduction [13].

Moreover, the success of virtual assistants like Erica has paved the way for further innovations in the banking sector. Many financial institutions are now exploring advanced AI technologies, such as natural language processing and machine learning, to create even more sophisticated automated customer service solutions.

5.2 Automation in Hospitality

The hospitality industry has embraced automation to enhance guest experiences and streamline operations, transforming the traditional hotel stay. Hilton's "Connected Room" technology exemplifies this shift, allowing guests to control various room features through their smartphones. This includes adjusting temperature, lighting, and entertainment systems, providing a personalized and convenient experience [12].

In addition to in-room automation, hotels have implemented automated check-in kiosks to reduce wait times and improve efficiency. These self-service stations enable guests to check in, receive their room keys, and even select their preferred room without interacting with staff. As a result, the role of front desk personnel has evolved from transaction processors to guest experience managers, focusing on providing personalized recommendations and addressing more complex guest needs.

The impact of automation in hospitality extends beyond guest-facing services. Behind the scenes, hotels are using AI and robotics to optimize housekeeping schedules, manage inventory, and predict maintenance needs. For example, some hotels have introduced robotic vacuum cleaners and automated linen delivery systems, freeing up staff to focus on tasks that require a human touch [13].

These technological advancements have not only improved operational efficiency but also contributed to increased guest satisfaction. A study by Cornell University's School of Hotel Administration found that hotels implementing automation technologies saw a 20% increase in guest satisfaction scores and a 15% reduction in operational costs [13].

As the hospitality industry continues to evolve, the integration of automation and AI is expected to play an increasingly crucial role in shaping the future of guest experiences and hotel operations.

Fig 2: Comparative Analysis: Automation Effects in Financial and Hospitality Services [12, 13]

6. Future Outlook

The impact of automation on service workers is expected to continue evolving, reshaping the landscape of various industries:

- Human-AI Collaboration:** Future workplaces will likely see increased collaboration between humans and AI systems, with each leveraging their unique strengths. This symbiotic relationship, often referred to as "augmented intelligence," aims to enhance human capabilities rather than replace them entirely [13]. For instance, in healthcare, AI algorithms can analyze vast amounts of medical data to assist doctors in making more accurate diagnoses, while human physicians provide the critical thinking and empathy necessary for patient care. Similarly, in customer service, AI chatbots can handle routine inquiries, allowing human agents to focus on complex issues that require emotional intelligence and nuanced problem-solving skills.
- Continuous Learning:** The rapid pace of technological change will necessitate a culture of continuous learning and skill development among workers. As automation takes over routine tasks, employees will need to adapt and acquire new skills to remain relevant in the job market [14]. This shift is already evident in many industries, with companies investing heavily in upskilling and reskilling programs. For example, Amazon's "Upskilling 2025" initiative aims to retrain 100,000 employees for in-demand jobs in machine learning, software engineering, and data science. Educational institutions and online learning platforms are also adapting their curricula to meet the evolving needs of the workforce, offering courses in emerging technologies and soft skills that complement AI capabilities.
- Personalization at Scale:** Automation will enable highly personalized service delivery at a scale previously impossible, creating new opportunities for workers skilled in experience design and data interpretation. This trend is particularly evident in retail and e-commerce, where AI-powered recommendation engines analyze customer data to provide tailored product suggestions [13]. In the financial sector, robo-advisors use algorithms to create personalized investment portfolios based on individual risk profiles and financial goals. As these technologies advance, there will be an increased demand for professionals who can design and optimize these personalized experiences, as well as interpret the vast amounts of data generated by these systems to drive business decisions.

The future of work in the age of automation will likely be characterized by a blend of human creativity, emotional intelligence, and technological proficiency. While some jobs may be displaced, new roles will emerge that focus on managing and enhancing AI systems, interpreting complex data patterns, and providing the human touch in increasingly automated environments. As such, both workers and organizations must remain adaptable and committed to ongoing learning to thrive in this evolving landscape.

7. Conclusion

The automation of service industry jobs presents a complex landscape of challenges and opportunities that will reshape the future of work. While job displacement remains a significant concern, automation also has the potential to augment human capabilities, improve working conditions, and create new, high-value roles that focus on creativity, emotional intelligence, and technological proficiency. Successfully navigating this transition will require concerted efforts from multiple stakeholders, including businesses, educational institutions, policymakers, and workers themselves. Key strategies include fostering a culture of continuous learning and skill development, ensuring ethical AI development and deployment, and implementing supportive policies that facilitate worker adaptation. As automation technologies continue to advance, the future workplace will likely be characterized by increased human-AI collaboration and the ability to deliver highly personalized services at scale. By embracing these changes and focusing on the unique strengths of human workers, we can work towards a future where automation enhances rather than diminishes the role of human workers in the service industry, ultimately leading to improved efficiency, job satisfaction, and economic growth.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Muro, R. Maxim, and J. Whiton, "Automation and Artificial Intelligence: How Machines Are Affecting People and Places," Brookings Institution, Jan. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.brookings.edu/research/automation-and-artificial-intelligence-how-machines-affect-people-and-places/>
- [2] C. B. Frey and M. A. Osborne, "The future of employment: How susceptible are jobs to computerisation?," *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, vol. 114, pp. 254-280, Jan. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0040162516302244>
- [3] Grand View Research, "Robotic Process Automation Market Size, Share & Trends Analysis Report By Type, By Service, By Application, By Deployment, By Organization, By Region, And Segment Forecasts, 2020 - 2027," Feb. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/robotic-process-automation-rpa-market>
- [4] Juniper Research, "Bank Cost Savings via Chatbots to Reach \$7.3 Billion by 2023, as Automated Customer Experience Evolves," Feb. 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.juniperresearch.com/press/bank-cost-savings-via-chatbots-reach-7-3bn-2023>
- [5] Deloitte Insights, "The Internet of Things: A technical primer," Feb. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www2.deloitte.com/us/en/insights/focus/internet-of-things/technical-primer.html>
- [6] J. Manyika et al., "Jobs lost, jobs gained: Workforce transitions in a time of automation," McKinsey Global Institute, Dec. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey/Industries/Public%20and%20Social%20Sector/Our%20Insights/What%20the%20future%20of%20work%20will%20mean%20for%20jobs%20skills%20and%20wages/MGI-Jobs-Lost-Jobs-Gained-Executive-summary-December-6-2017.pdf>
- [7] World Bank Group, "World Development Report 2019: The Changing Nature of Work," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/wdr2019>

- [8] World Economic Forum, "The Future of Jobs Report 2020," Oct. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-future-of-jobs-report-2020>
- [9] Pew Research Center, "Public Attitudes Toward Computer Algorithms," Nov. 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2018/11/16/public-attitudes-toward-computer-algorithms/>
- [10] J. Bessen, "How Computer Automation Affects Occupations: Technology, Jobs, and Skills," Boston Univ. School of Law, Law and Economics Research Paper No. 15-49, Oct. 2016. [Online]. Available: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2690435
- [11] European Commission, "Proposal for a Regulation laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence," Apr. 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/proposal-regulation-laying-down-harmonised-rules-artificial-intelligence>
- [12] S. Marr, "AI in Banking: The Reality Behind the Hype," Forbes, May 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ft.com/content/b497a134-2d21-11e8-a34a-7e7563b0b0f4>
- [13] E. Brynjolfsson and A. McAfee, "The Business of Artificial Intelligence," Harvard Business Review, July 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://hbr.org/2017/07/the-business-of-artificial-intelligence>
- [14] World Economic Forum, "The Future of Jobs Report 2020," Oct. 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.weforum.org/reports/the-future-of-jobs-report-2020>

Citation: Shradha Kohli, The Impact of Automation on Service Workers: A Technical Analysis, International Journal of Engineering and Technology Research (IJETR), 9(2), 2024, pp. 492–504.

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJETR/VOLUME_9_ISSUE_2/IJETR_09_02_043.pdf

Abstract:

https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJETR_09_02_043

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com